

FEATURES OF NEGOTIATIONS IN ARAB COUNTRIES.

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Annotation.

this article is aimed at showing that the world of the current Arab countries has a special place in international relations, in which representatives of the Arab rasimy are aimed at showing and taxing only their characteristic features in negotiations with various partners.

Keywords.

international relations, Arab world, official negotiations, diplomacy, diplomatic pratakol, diplomatic label.

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dannaya statya napravlena na to, chtobi pokazat, chto Mir nineshnix arabskix stran zanimaet osoboe mesto v mejdunarodnix otnosheniyax, V kotorix predstaviteli arabskoy rasi stremyatsya demonstrrovat I oblagat nalogom tolko svoi characternie cherti v peregovorax s razlichnimi partnerami.

Keywords.

Mejdunarodnie otnosheniya, Arabsky Mir, officialnie peregovori, diplomacy, Diplomaticheskyy pratakol, Diplomaticheskyy etiquette.

The one who trusted the structure of today's jaxon state structures can see its abundance and non-border edges. The fact that the number of direct member and indirect member states of the United Nations is now more than two hundred, and each has its own sovereignty, it is this jaxon organization that has established itself in all international documents.

A sovereign state is defined as a key participant in international relations as a sovereign subject of a sovereign state – international IOC. As a subject of international law, the state is an official representative of political democracy in the International Circle, full of legal authority over all rights and their implementation. The Sovereign of the state is associated with its independence neither only in its own god, but also within the framework of international relations. Because the state itself develops and determines the norms of international law, determines the activities of international organizations and wraps the procedure for international law, which does not limit tarnib beyond the state itself to the term Hecht kim. Such procedures are prescribed by UN member states, based on its charter.

Since these provisions give all states a full chance to assert their sovereignty, then to what extent, political, economic, cultural status they have in international relations, they give the right to determine their diplomatic status. This rule gives all states in international monasteries the right to determine and establish their own procedures, based on their desires, national, historical, cultural, religious, spiritual and other mental characteristics.

Therefore, international relations in their interrelationships, in their conduct of relations, diplomacy (France.dipomatic) is one of the main tools for the implementation of the foreign policy of states. This term, in the order of negotiation, establishes the rules of etiquette, traditions and conditions that are observed during the International agreed protocol, correspondence, etiquette, exchange of representatives of their own range, sending and receiving couriers, as well as holding meetings, conversations and reception ceremonies.

In diplomatic relations, the protocol is a set of rules adopted in the general international mices, the observance of which is treasured to improve the relationship in its own way, as well as the fact that its violation on the contrary is a sign that there is inadequacy in relations.

The second, within the rules of the diplomatic protocol, is a label in the diplomatic language, which means the declaration of respect and expressiveness of one's own aro, adopted at direct meetings of Representatives. Etiquette (from French – etiquette-label, writing) is the rules of conduct of people in society that support their ideas about the rules of etiquette that are relevant to society, the requirements that bulib officials must follow in their interpersonal communication. Their careless execution required extreme subtlety, which could lead international relations to peaceful or turbulent (beating) holites.

Diplomatic etiquette is the rule of Conduct for diplomats and other dignitaries during various diplomatic events, at receptions, during visits, during negotiations, when communicating with each other.

Diplomatic etiquette is very diverse. It includes meetings, congratulations, the organization of banquets, the holding of visits, the etiquette of conversation, negotiations and a special diplomatic ceremony.

The purpose and essence of the topic we propose is to seek to open up the question of the existence and existence of some peculiarities in the relations of peoples, countries and states in the era of radical changes in the conditions of globalization of the current world, albeit a little. In particular, the issue is the imposition of precisely the features of negotiation in Arab countries.

The history of the Arab world has had its own cultural way of life for two thousand years and has its place in the history of mankind as a jixonshumul. We see that the civilization of the "Islamic age of Engraving", which began with the early middle captives, is directly and indirectly related to the historical vocations of the Arab people. Is it impossible to clarify the topic without fail that the rise of the caliphate brought the first period of Engraving into the history of man through the rise that led him almost to the politics and culture of the medieval duyosi.

True, although we can see that in the middle and late Middle Ages davirs, as well as in the new era of history, the political, economic, cultural taisri of Arab states and countries have subsided, we can see that Arab countries have not lost their historical place in the political culture of the world. As a result of the change of the world's political system in the late 20th and early 21st centuries and the change to the side of hydrocarbon fuel (oil) in the economic priority, the advantage and dominance of the countries of the Arab world from many Jihad went to the end. As a result, Arab countrymen introduced into the lake the possibilities of restoring their historical, political cultures and being able to show it.

Today, the countries of the world have begun to fully distinguish themselves in their policies with the countries of the Arab Peninsula. After all, the relevance of our chosen topic is that it will never be a mistake if we say that it is more and more complete.

We see that the policy that Arab diplomacy has pursued in the history of mankind since the Middle Ages is being carried out in Kham almost unchanged Khol. In this, it was necessary to insist that communication and relations with the Arabs in the first goal could not be excluded from their specifics.

Shubhasis may occur when, in their internationally accepted relations, diplomatic protocol, etiquette standards, rules are used, with representatives of

Arab countries, to conduct negotiation meetings, without prejudice to their specifics, to bring negative results.

Unlike Western representatives, Arabs do not use logical reasoning in negotiations, but personal arguments, appeals and strict beliefs. During negotiations in Arab countries, one should not be afraid of long disputes and heated discussions, negati Arabs seek to bring their work as positive as possible. In the negotiations in the Arab country; sincerity, truthfulness, highly appreciated by representatives of Arab culture. Arab culture is a polyactive-culture, in which great importance is attached to the hierarchy, which creates favorable conditions for interaction and proper communication. An extrovert psychotype dominates among polyactive cultures. Usually representatives of Italy, Latin America and Arab countries are bright samples. When meeting with representatives of Arab countries, it is necessary to behave more extroverted- (a person of an openly polite character turns his experience and interests into objects of the outside world). The interlocutor should not remain at the usual distance, you need to approach the interlocutor with your knowledge and attitude. Otherwise, he may go as far as to perceive distance as a sign of your coldness or even hostile attitude towards him.

In negotiations, Arabs always strive to maintain an atmosphere of mutual trust. Arab, the partner will be happy to demonstrate his charm, oratory ability, understanding and professionalism. The emergence of negotiators in negotiations with the Arab side, gifts, etiquette, distribution of titles and positions of Representa.

In the Muslim world, a foreigner cannot address a woman with questions or requests, which is considered indecent, all discussions are conducted with men. When meeting in Arab countries, men hug, lightly touch each other with their cheeks, stroking their back and shoulders, but such signs of attention are possible only among themselves and do not apply to strangers.

At the first acquaintance, your Arabic interlocutor will show you sincerity and politeness. This is not a claim, but a tribute to tradition: among Arabs, the opinion prevails that only such behavior is worthy of a Muslim. The next conversation can go less smoothly. Arab interlocutors avoid clear, specific answers in every way "yes" or "no". Instead, they say, "Inshahallah" or "Mashallah" ("may God give" or "may God Save"). The Arabic concept of etiquette forbids the interlocutor to resort to direct answers, to be persistent. Arabs also avoid haste during the conversation and always strive to "save the face" of both themselves and their interlocutors. It is considered necessary to leave the opportunity for further contacts. Arab entrepreneurs express their refusal in the most gentle, veiled form.

Although representatives of the United Arab Emirates are known for their knowledge of English, an important part of business etiquette in this country is the translation of official documents into Arabic. As a rule, business representatives of Saudi Arabia also have excellent knowledge of English. Business cards here must be written in English. Conversational English is also spoken by most Egyptians, as it is taught in Egyptian schools. Some Egyptians may say several phrases in French

، نعم- شمسابل بيل بيليشلار تيليني ناذب إنجليس أميرل يكلاري العربيه يرلا شغان
القاعدة. تارجيمات يديغان العربيه الإجراءات من مهم جزء هو إت يكينغ-إيد شت مامراكات دا بو
الطول كامل إنجليز، شونينجديك، فاكيلاري الأعمال السعوديه العربيه الاممكة، تقول
تحدث. الشرط أيزيد ليشي تيليدا إنجليس فيسديتكالار ييردا بو. الأنا بيليجا
فرانز عبارات بعض تكون قد بمصر كتب لأنه أيضا القديم المصري تيليدا الإنجليزي
إيد تشلاري المصريه نيتا بيرت ييليدا

When we are negotiating with the Arabs, we are talking about Lake hares, gestures, imitations, table and tabletop items, touching the sound from them, Ham has its meaning and influence. Especially the contact of one of the bodies can be manoga eaga in aloxia. For example, it can be said that during the recent official visit of US President Joe Baydon to Saudi Arabia, the Saudi Sultan did not open the palm of the hand at the time of the lake boredom, seeing the fists in the form of a fight against one another, which was a sign that coldness had fallen between the two states.

As a conclusion, it is worth saying that the culture of diplomacy is a kind of Science, in which, while such subtle concepts as pratakol, etiquette have generally accepted procedures and rules, we see that the peculiarities of every People, Country, exist in ham. In this, Neither only political, economic, positive, but also historical, cultural, spiritual religious correspondence can be household features. The diplomacy of the Arab countries has a deep historical, religious tradition, kholda is full of qualities of a manarchic structure in the political range of the people. Studying such features as

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